

Financial Literacy in India: An Overview on Literature

Mr.S.Karthik, M.Com.,M.Phil.,SET.,

Assistant Professor & Ph.D Research Scholar

PG Department of Commerce (Shift-II)

Sacred Heart College (Autonomous), Tirupattur (Vellore District)

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Dr.K.Antony Baskaran, M.Com.,M.Phil.,B.Ed.,PGDPM.,Ph.D.,

Associate Professor and Research Supervisor

PG & Research Department of Commerce (Shift-I)

Sacred Heart College (Autonomous), Tirupattur Vellore District

Abstract

Financial literacy is the combination of the knowledge, ability and attitude towards the financial matters of any individual. It supports to make informed about the decisions and well-being of the individuals. Low level of financial literacy habitually prevents the individuals from making the right choices regarding financial decisions. To achieve the objectives, the individuals must invest their savings in the right investment alternatives. The objective of this study is to learn the level of financial literacy in India by using the literature based analysis. Secondary data was collected from various websites, journals, research papers and articles.

Keywords: Financial Literacy, Financial Behaviour, Financial Decisions.

Introduction

Financial literacy is the foremost challenge faced by all the nations globally. Financial literacy is the blend of one’s acquaintance, skill and attitude towards financial matters. It helps to make informed on the decisions and well-being of the individuals.

In today’s world which has a market with complicated products, the need for financial literacy becomes predictable. The country like India which has highly havingyoungergeneration, the government is in a situation to increase the level of financial literacy among the people.

The government of India and other private institutions have taken the hierarchy through financial education programmes. Financial literacy goes beyond the provision of financial information and advice. It is the ability to know, monitor, and efficiently use financial sources to enhance the welfare and economic refuge of an individual, his family, and his business.

The Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD) defines the financial literacy as, “A combination of awareness, acquaintance, skill, attitude and behavior necessary to make sound financial decisions and ultimately achieve individual financial well-being.”

Financial literacy is mainly concerned with the better planning of retirement life, gradual wealth accumulation and better financial decision making. So, to be financially literate becomes important from the initial stages of one's career. But due to some personal or professional hindrances, they become financially illiterate.

This leaves them with incompetent knowledge about financial dealings, unacceptable decisions, etc., and so they have to be enhanced with financial knowledge and tools which are needed to make informed decisions.

Financial literacy impacts the promotion of financial inclusion which ultimately results in the financial stability of any economy. The need for financial literacy in India has benefited importance because of the low level of literacy and the large section of the population which is financially excluded from the formal financial setup.

Researches have been conducted worldwide for measuring the level of financial literacy. And also financial literacy survey has been conducted at country level by the governments. Most of the surveys have thrown light on their poor level of financial literacy. This study focuses on financial literacy among the people to examine how well-equipped they are to make financial decisions. The research also concentrates on their sources, their knowledge and the challenges faced by them in financial matters.

Need for the Study

Complicated financial products, low level of awareness and lack of knowledge about financial matters make the want of financial literacy noteworthy. The level of financial literacy differs from individual to individual. The gender gap also plays an important role in deciding the level of financial literacy.

A woman's decision or relationship with money is often determined by her personal life experience. Emotion, money and family are interlinked in the life of a woman. Lack of equipped access of consistent information to make the informed decision leads to a low level of confidence and knowledge about financial issues.

The reforms introduced in financial markets have reduced the scope of governments and employers in supporting the employees to plan their future financial needs. So, the responsibility of managing and deciding their future financial needs has increased among the young employees.

High job insecurity, uncertain income and easy access to consumption credit have a great influence on their financial behavior. Very less research has been done on financial literacy.

A country like India with high young demographic dividend and socio-economic diversities should undergo researches in this topic. With 65 percent of its population under the age of 35 years, India today assertions one of the largest available workforces in the world.

A large segment of this demographic belongs to the younger generations. So, measuring financial literacy among the people under the age of 35 becomes more important.

Objectives of the Study

The Objectives of the Study Include

1. The foremost objective of the research is to study the level of financial literacy in India by using literature-based analysis;
2. To understand the challenges and goals that the youth have with regards to the financial matters; and
3. To find out the relationship between financial literacy and various demographic and socio-economic factors.

Review of Literature

Increased variety of financial products and the instability of the global economy in the twenty-first century caused increasing complexity of financial decisions and also caused consumers to face the challenges in economic and financial activities. For this reason, in the last decade, the significance of financial management skills in personal and work life has increased and researches in this area have been done.

Some of the reviews of the existing studies are listed below.

Financial literacy was strongly related to socio-demographic characteristics and family financial sophistication. Specifically, a college-educated male whose parents had stocks and retirement savings was about 45 percentage points more likely to know about risk diversification than a female with less than a high school education whose parents were not wealthy (Lusardi, Mitchell and Curto 2006).

Studies by Marcolin and Abraham (2006); Schuchardt et al., (2008); Remund (2010) and Huston (2010) found that “Despite the rapid growth of interest in and funding for financial literacy and financial education programs, it remains the case that the field of financial literacy has a major obstacle to overcome: the lack of a widely disseminated measure of financial literacy, developed through rigorous psychometric analyses”.

Sages and Grable, (2009) in their study found that “the individuals who have the lowest level of financial risk tolerance is the least competent regarding financial matters, have the lowest subjective evaluation of net worth and are less satisfied with their financial management skills. The level of financial risk tolerance of the individuals determines the financial behavior”.

Agarwalla Sobhesh Kumar, Barua Samir, Jacob Joshy, Jayanth R. Varma(2012) conducted a study among 3000 individuals and found that “Financial knowledge among Indians is very low then the International standards. But the financial behavior and attitude of the employees and retired seems to be positive. The financial knowledge among the women is marginally high than the men.”

Ansong and Gyensare (2012) conducted a study among 250 UG and PG University students of Cape Coast reveals that “the age and work experience are positively related to financial literacy. Also, the mother’s education is positively correlated with respondents’ financial literacy. But, level of study, work location, father’s education, access to media and the source of education on money has no influence on financial literacy”.

Puneet Bhushan et al. (2013), surveyed 516 salaried individuals in Himachal Pradesh using multistage sampling to check the financial literacy level. It is found that the overall literacy level is low and the financial literacy level of the male is more than females. Level of education, income, nature of employment and place of work influence on financial literacy whereas geographical region does not influence financial literacy.

Kamal Gupta et al. (2014), assessed the level of financial literacy amongst 87 micro Entrepreneurs of Kangra district of Himalaya Pradesh based on record keeping, various institutional awareness, savings, investment plans, savings management and various loan products. It is found that most of the respondents are responsive to bank loans, less awareness of other financial institutions.

Lavanya Rekha Bahadur (2015), analyzed two pillars of the economy: financial literacy and financial inclusion and its current scenario as well as common people perspective about financial instruments. Data collected from 202 Mumbai and Thane district individuals. It is found that level of financial literacy is very low and suggested to encourage financial literacy from school level, national level programs and seep effort to the grass root level.

Ratna Achuta Paluri (2016), analyzed factors influencing financial attitudes of Indian women to classify Indian women based on attitude with nine variables: anxiety, interest in financial issues, intuitive decisions, precautionary savings, free-spending, materialistic and fatalistic attitude, propensity to plan for long and short-term financial goals. The study used confirmatory factor analysis to cluster the women of Nashik city.

Challenges of the Youth on Financial Literacy

Financial illiteracy affects all ages and all socioeconomic levels especially the youths. The lack of financial literacy may lead to poor financial choices that can have negative consequences on the all-round well-being of an individual, particularly the youngsters.

It can cause many people to become victims of predatory lending, subprime mortgages, or fraud and high-interest rates, resulting in bad credit or bankruptcy. The lack of financial literacy can lead to large amounts of debt and poor financial decisions. For example, the advantages or disadvantages of fixed and variable interest rates are concepts that are easier to understand if you possess financial literacy skills.

Research studies on financial literacy have shown that most financial consumers cannot understand and effectively manage basic financial concepts or products. A lack of financial literacy education is responsible for poor money management skills and below-par financial planning for business and retirement.

Here are some of the effects that financial illiteracy can have:

- Prohibits individuals from becoming productive members of the economy and society by engulfing them in a cycle of ever-increasing debt;
- Decreases the chances of effectively assessing financial risks or opportunities. This makes financial choices riskier and potentially damaging;
- Hinders anyone seeking to be financially secure. For example, financial illiteracy can increase the chances of losses due to fraud or scams; and
- Magnifies the physical and mental issues associated with being in debt and lessens the chances of finding an appropriate debt solution.

These are some of the detrimental effects that financial illiteracy can have on people of all ages and all walks of life.

Demographic Factors and Financial Literacy

Various studies have shown a significant relationship between demographic variables and financial literacy. The main factors considered include gender, age and education.

Gender

Financial literacy may be shaped by the different roles that men and women play in the society which are determined by their gender. While women traditionally did the housework, took care of the home and the children, men were the providers and not only took care of themselves but also their families.

Age

Age has been determined to have an impact on financial literacy. It was specifically observed that at a younger age, an individual is likely to have less income than their needs. These needs include the need for basic needs such as food, shelter, clothing education and medical care. An individual at this stage of the life cycle will have very little savings as they are likely to take up debt to be able to meet these needs.

Education

Education is an important determinant of financial literacy. The level of education has been found to have a positive relationship with both basic and advanced financial literacy. Those completing their university or college education were found to have a higher score for the financial literacy test as compared to those whose highest level of education was at the high school level. With higher

education, people are expected to have a higher understanding of financial matters and to make the better investment choice.

Socio-Economic Factors and Financial Literacy

Various studies have identified some socio-economic variables that influence financial literacy. In this study, the focus is on wealth, employment status and sources of information.

Income

Financial literacy levels in many research studies have been associated with income and wealth levels. Many studies have associated high levels of financial literacy with wealth. According to the reason that wealth has a positive impact on financial literacy is because the desire for wealth accumulation motivates one desire to increase their financial knowledge.

Employment Status

Higher financial literacy scores have been reported among those who are in professional occupations and also among those that hold managerial positions. As per the survey carried out in the UAE among investors reported that investors whose area of specialization career wise was in finance, banking and investments reported the highest levels of financial literacy as compared to those investors whose did not specialize in the professional field of finance

Sources of Information

Many studies link financial literacy to the sources of information for financial decision making. Investors rely on many sources of information which they use in making different financial decisions. This includes financial statements, other financial publications, government publications, newspapers, magazines the internet, financial consultants, family, colleagues and friends, Family, peers, school, and the media have been identified as the primary sources of financial information

Conclusion

The rapid growth of the Indian economy and complex financial market leads to improper financial decisions. To achieve the financial objectives, one has to possess basic financial skills, awareness, knowledge, attitude and well demonstrated the behavior. Various studies reveal that the financial literacy level in India is very low, especially women and youngsters who are struggling with their basic financial knowledge. Although many initiatives from RBI and government on financial literacy improvement financial literacy level is still low. It is necessary to mend the level of literacy through new initiatives.

References

- ECD INFE (2011) Measuring Financial Literacy: Core Questionnaire in Measuring Financial Literacy: Questionnaire and Guidance Notes for conducting an Internationally Comparable Survey of Financial Literacy. Paris: OECD.
- Harsha V Jariwala, "Analysis of Financial Literacy Level of Retail Individual Investors of Gujarat State and Its Effect on Investment Decision," *Journal of Business & Finance Librarianship*, November 2014, PP. 133-158.
- Kamal Gupta and Jatinder Kaur, "A study of Financial Literacy among Micro Entrepreneurs in District Kangra," *IJRBM*, Vol-2, Issue-2, February 2014, PP. 63-70.
- K N Narendra, "Financial Literacy: A revolution waiting to happen, Proceeding of COFP Convention 2014".

- Lavanya Rekha Bahadur, "Financial Literacy: The Indian Story," World Journal of Social Sciences, Vol-5, Issue-3, September 2015, PP. 45-57.
- Priyanka Agarwal, Dr. Suman Yadav, Radhika Kureel, International Journal of Advance Research in Science and Engineering, Vol-1, Issue-1, 2015, PP. 54-61.
- Puneet Bhushan, Yajulu Medury, "Financial Literacy and its Determinants," International Journal of Engineering, Business and Enterprise Applications (IJEBEA), Vol. 4, Issue -2, May-2013, PP. 155-160.
- Ratna Achuta Paluri, Saloni Mehra, "Financial attitude based segmentation of women in India: an exploratory study," Vol. 34 Issue 5, January 2016, PP. 670 - 689.
- Sumit Agarwal, Gene Amromin, Douglas D Evan off, "Financial Literacy and Financial Planning: Evidence from India," SSRN Electronic Journal, December 2010.
- Visa, Financial Literacy Survey, Indians among least financially literate people globally, Firstpost.com, December 2014.
- V Mathavathani, Dr. M Velumani, "A Study on Financial Literacy among Rural Women in Tamilnadu," Indian Journal of Applied Research, Volume-4, Issue-12, December 2014, PP. 556-557.

Web Sources

- <http://a4eindiamord.in/MarketScan.aspx>
- <http://meeasites.luc.edu/volume19/pdfs/2-5%20Financial%20literacy%20in%20developing%20countries.pdf>
- <http://mgt.sjp.ac.lk/fin/financial-literacy-survey/>
- <http://www.agribusinesszambia.com/zcf-zamcom-ink-financial-literacy-deal/>
- http://www.dartmouth.edu/%7Ealusardi/Papers/Financial_literacy_young.pdf
- <http://www.ijrbsm.org/papers/v4-i6/4.pdf>
- <http://www.imperialjournals.com/index.php/IJIR/article/download/4779/4589>
- <https://acadpubl.eu/jsi/2018-118-18/articles/18b/54.pdf>
- https://www.greatlakes.edu.in/herald/pdfs/march-2015/Article_3.pdf
- <https://www.redstareducation.co.uk/blog/the-effects-of-financial-illiteracy/>